

Supplementary Material for: A SLR of Modern AI-Driven SCA on NIST’s PQC Standards

Edgard Nicéas Arcoverde Gusmão Lima^{1,2}[0000–0002–5241–8092], Fábio Wladimir Monteiro Maia^{1,2}[0000–0001–9733–1591], Tiago Alessandro Espínola Ferreira³[0000–0002–2131–9825], and Danilo Monteiro Ribeiro²[0000–0001–7393–729X]

¹ CISSA, CESAR, Recife, Brazil
enagl@cesar.org.br, fwmm@cesar.org.br

² CESAR School, Recife, Brazil

enagl@cesar.edu.br, fwmm@cesar.edu.br, dmr@cesar.school

³ PPGIA, Universidade Federal Rural de Pernambuco (UFRPE), Recife, Brazil
tiago.espinola@ufrpe.br

Introduction

This document provides the supplementary material and replication data for the paper entitled:

“A SLR of Modern AI-Driven SCA on NIST’s PQC Standards.”

It contains methodological information, extended tables, data extraction summaries, quality assessment results, and the validated Gold Set used to construct and evaluate the database search strategy.

The material provided here enables full transparency and reproducibility of the study selection, data extraction, and quality assessment processes described in the main paper.

Methodology Details

Databases Used

- **IEEE Xplore:** A comprehensive database covering key conferences and journals in hardware security and electronics [16].
- **ACM Digital Library:** The main source for publications from the Association for Computing Machinery, including flagship security conferences like CCS and ASIACCS [3].
- **Engineering Village:** A comprehensive engineering database covering a wide range of technical literature, also provided by Elsevier [9].
- **ScienceDirect & Scopus:** Major interdisciplinary databases from Elsevier, providing broad coverage of scientific and technical literature [11,10].
- **SpringerLink (including LNCS):** Publisher of major cryptography conference proceedings, most notably the *Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems* (TCHES), the flagship journal for side-channel research [34].

- **IACR ePrint Archive:** The primary repository for pre-print cryptographic research, essential for capturing the latest findings [17].

Table 1: PICOC Framework for Search Query Definition

PICOC Element	Definition for this SLR	Keywords and Synonyms
Population	NIST Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) Round 4 finalists and standardized algorithms.	"post-quantum cryptography", "PQC", "quantum-resistant", "Kyber", "ML-KEM", "Dilithium", "ML-DSA", "SPHINCS+", "SLH-DSA", "FALCON", "FN-DSA", "HQC"
Intervention	The application of AI, Machine Learning, or Deep Learning models as the primary analysis tool or distinguisher in an attack.	"artificial intelligence", "AI", "machine learning", "ML", "deep learning", "DL", "neural network", "CNN", "recurrent neural network", "RNN", "generative adversarial network", "GAN", "transformer", "reinforcement learning", "graph neural network", "GNN", "support vector machine", "SVM", "random forest", "gradient boosting", "computational intelligence", "data mining", "predictive modeling"
Context	Side-channel analysis of physical cryptographic implementations.	"side-channel", "side channel", "SCA", "power analysis", "timing attack", "electromagnetic analysis"

Table 2: Revised Gold Set for Database Search Validation

#	Article Title / Reference	Justification for Inclusion
1	Deep learning enhanced side channel analysis on CRYSTALS-Kyber (Hoang et al., 2024) [14]	This paper presents the first known side-channel attack on Kyber using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), recovering the private key with only 50 traces in a practical, black-box scenario.
2	Breaking the Blindfold: Deep Learning-based Blind Side-channel Analysis (Rezaeizade et al., 2024) [31]	A cutting-edge paper from a top-tier venue (USENIX Security) that introduces a novel deep learning framework and validates it with a successful attack on Kyber.
3	Single-Trace Side-Channel Attacks on CRYSTALS-Dilithium: Myth or Reality? (Wang et al., 2023) [41]	This paper details a profiled deep learning-assisted power analysis attack against CRYSTALS-Dilithium using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), achieving the first successful full key recovery from a single power trace by targeting the secret key unpacking procedure.
4	A side-channel attack on a masked hardware implementation of CRYSTALS-Kyber (Ji & Dubrova, 2025) [19]	This journal paper describes a profiled deep learning-assisted attack using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) against a first-order masked hardware (FPGA) implementation of Kyber, demonstrating the first practical message recovery attack on a protected hardware version of the algorithm.
5	Breaking a Fifth-Order Masked Implementation of CRYSTALS-Kyber by Copy-Paste (Dubrova et al., 2023) [8]	This highly significant paper from APKC'23 demonstrates a neural network attack that breaks a very high-order (fifth-order) masked implementation of Kyber using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) trained with a novel "recursive learning" method, pushing the state-of-the-art.
6	Curse of Re-encryption: A Generic Power/EM Analysis on Post-Quantum KEMs (Ueno et al., 2022) [38]	This foundational paper details a generic side-channel attack against numerous post-quantum KEMs, including Kyber, and validates its practicality by using a deep learning-based (CNN/MLP) distinguisher to create a plaintext-checking oracle.
7	Single Trace Analysis of Visible vs. Invisible Leakage for Comparison-Operation-Based CDT Sampling (Choi et al., 2024) [7]	This paper proposes a deep learning-based side-channel attack using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) to recover CDT sampling values from the FALCON signature scheme on an ARM Cortex-M4 by exploiting a novel "invisible" vulnerability in constant-time comparison operations.

Summary of Data Extracted from Primary Studies

Table 3: Summary of MLP SCAs against Dilithium and FALCON

MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron neural network)

Dilithium (SW): Signing + key-gen; secret-coefficient labeling (s_1, s_2). single-trace profiling attack on NTT (s_1 : 100%) and sampling/addition/rounding/packing (s_2 : $\leq 98\%$). 60k traces (45k train/5k val/10k attack). NN: BN-Dense-BN-ReLU-Dense-Softmax (Nadam). Full s_1 recovery; s_2 up to 98% per op. [13].

Dilithium (SW): Signing; $y_{i,j}$ zero/nonzero labeling; Four MLP classifiers (Dense/Dropout stacks; up to $\approx 3.7 \times 10^5$ params) tuned via Hyperband; 548-sample trace windows. Profiling on Device A; attack uses $\sim 100k$ signing traces; classifier accuracy ≈ 0.999 . Full s_1 recovery and end-to-end **key extraction**; Level-2 break requires ≈ 10 min of signatures. [22]

Dilithium-2 (SW): Signing; coefficient-value labeling ($-2..2$) during `skDecode`. Eight MLP classifiers (440-sample input; 5 classes; Nadam, 100 epochs) trained on 3.2M segments ($< 10h$ profiling). Single-trace coefficient recovery ≈ 0.92 ; full s_1 recovery with single trace succeeds with 9% (linear-equation variant). 1000 traces \rightarrow 100% **key recovery**; BKZ variant also feasible without t_0 . [41]

Dilithium-2 (SW): Signing; $LSB(t_0[i])$ labeling during `polyt0_unpack`. 168 models (8 coeff.-types; 512-256-256 FC layers); trained on 2.56M segments (550-sample windows). Majority voting yields ≈ 57 wrong LSBs; unanimous voting reduces to ≈ 15 with ≈ 126 undecided. With 960 averaged traces, 80.5% of (s_1, s_2) coefficients recovered with 0.875 probability; combined with partial t_0 recovery gives ≈ 0.7 full s_1 **key recovery**. [40]

Dilithium-2 (M, SW): Signing; NTT-encryption (unmasked) and sparse multiplication (masked). Boolean masking defeated. Profiling via MLP (BN-Dense-BN-ReLU-Dense-Softmax; Adam, CE loss; inputs normalized to $[-1, 1]$). Labels = 3Byte of $s_1[i]$ (unmasked) or all 256 byte-values of masked shares. Unmasked: 2000 profiling traces, 8000 attack traces \rightarrow 100% full-key recovery. Masked: 9000 profiling, 8000 attack traces \rightarrow 100% **full-key recovery** (single-trace). [21]

FALCON (SW): CDT sampling; Visible early-stop leakage on AVR and invisible Hamming-weight leakage on ARM defeat comparison-op "constant-time" CDT. BN-Dense-BN-Dense-BN-Dense trained on 112k traces (736-sample windows; Adam lr= 10^{-4} ; 10 epochs). Test accuracy 99.97%, F1=1.0. Single-trace recovery of CDT output (14 classes). Leakage assessment only, no key/message recovery. [7]

(SW)Firmware, (HW)FPGA, (M)Masked

Table 4: Summary of MLP SCAs against Kyber

MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron neural network)

Kyber-512 (M,HW): Decapsulation; HD(m[i-1],m[i]) labeling; 1000 profiling traces \rightarrow 255k segments; MLP architecture with BN/Dense/ReLU layers; single-trace HD accuracy \approx 0.615; full-message success: 97.7% with 299 traces, 99.7% with 399; cross-device profiling reduces success to 94.8%; training hyperparameters explicitly listed [19].

Kyber-768 (M,SW): Decapsulation; m[i] labeling; ω =1st-5th-order masking broken via recursive-training (weight transfer across ω). 30k profiling traces \rightarrow 960k; cyclic rotations amplify determiners (0x0000/0xFFFF). Single-trace bit accuracy 0.999 \rightarrow 0.979 ($\omega = 1 \rightarrow 5$); message success 78.9% \rightarrow 0.56%. For $\omega = 5$, majority voting with 5 power traces reaches 87%. Encapsulation attack, labeling HW(m[i]), failed even unmasked [8].

Kyber-768 (M,SW): Decapsulation; polytomsg(m)[i] labeling; first-order masked poly tomsg attacked. 50k traces; bitwise segmentation ($256 \times 3 \times 225$); MLP achieves 90% validation accuracy and 99% **key-coefficient recovery** in 65h; Attack requires chosen ciphertexts, preprocessing and ECT-based error correction [12]. See Table 6 for failing RNN attack of this paper.

Kyber-768 (M,S,SW): Decapsulation; HW(msg byte) labeling; countermeasures evaluated: masking, noise, random delay, clock jitter. classifier with several hidden layers; trimming Masked_Encode boosts accuracy 30% \rightarrow 88%; Decode DL accuracy drops to 0.37% under N0.1; Masked_Decode <1% accuracy with noise or AR200 jitter [15].

Kyber-768 (M,S,SW): Decapsulation; HD(m[i-1],m[i]) labeling; Single-trace DL-SCA + **Fault Injection** voltage-glitch bypass of Fisher-Yates shuffle; 10k profiling traces \rightarrow 2.56M segments, one attack trace; MLP (320-dim input, Nadam, \leq 250 epochs) predicts message bits; full-message success 0.122 \rightarrow 0.887 (32-bit enumeration) \rightarrow 0.969 (64-bit enumeration). [18].

Kyber-768 (HW): Decapsulation; m[i] labeling; Profiling uses 200k traces \rightarrow 6.4M samples; MLP (BN-Dense-BN-ReLU-Dense-Softmax, 21k params) trained with Nadam (100 epochs). Attack uses $256 \times 4 \times 5$ traces via 4-sliced multi-bit error injection, recovering all messages with byte-rank ≤ 3 (enumeration $\leq 4^{32} = 2^{64}$). Recovering messages from 7 chosen ciphertexts enables long-term **secret-key extraction** [20].

Kyber-768 (SW, Masked): Decapsulation; first-order masked message encoding. Profiling (BN-Dense-BN-Dense-BN-Dense, ReLU, Softmax, Dropout 0.5) on joined-share traces (input=380). 1000 traces \rightarrow 32k samples; Adam, CE loss; val. acc. reaches 100%. Single-trace message recovery; 2-stage CCA-assisted attack recovers **full secret key** with 9 traces (\approx 100% success), or 18 traces with negligible brute-force. [39]

Kyber512 (SW): Decapsulation; labels=HW(R1 reduction, profiled) \rightarrow applied to R2 (key-dependent). MLP 160-100-40-12, ReLU/Softmax, trained on 10^6 R1 sub-traces (SGD, lr=0.01). Validation accuracy 68.6%. **Key-recovery** via probabilistic accumulation: 76.9% (5 traces) \rightarrow 100% (11 traces). [44]

Kyber (SW): Decapsulation; Blind SCA via DL-BSCA using MLP classifier with MC-labeling (GMM on 100 PoIs). 80k profiling traces; 20k attack; label encoding $(B+1)h_m+h_y$ with \approx 1.2% correct labels. Hyperparameter search over 100 models (dropout/no-dropout). Achieves GE=9.2 for s_0 recovery under blind conditions. Has been outperformed by its CNN version [31].

Kyber (SW, Masked): Decapsulation; FO-based re-encryption leakage through masked software PRF. Attack uses a 5-layer MLP (FC1-FC5) with Sigmoid output for two-class (label) distinguishing of PRF inputs. Fully-connected design chosen to capture multivariate leakage of masked SW. Produces a reliable plaintext-checking oracle enabling adaptive re-encryption; key recovery succeeds within \leq 60k oracle traces. [38]. **HQC** was included analytically, but it wasn't really attacked.

(SW)Firmware, (HW)FPGA, (R)RTL, (M)Masked, (S)Shuffled, (A)Anti-Tampering Cover

Table 5: Summary of CNN SCAs

CNN (Convolutional neural network)
<p>Kyber (SW): Decapsulation; Blind SCA via DL-BSCA using CNN trained with MC-labeling (GMM on 100 PoIs). 80k profiling traces; 20k attack; same noisy-label encoding $(B+1)h_m+h_y$. Hyperparameter search over 100 architectures. Best CNN+MC configuration reaches GE=2.01, successfully recovering s_0 under blind conditions. Has outperformed its MLP version [31].</p>
<p>Kyber (M,SW,HW): Decapsulation; FO-based re-encryption leakage via PRF executions. CNN distinguisher (Conv1-Conv6 + FC, Sigmoid) trained to classify PRF inputs as reference vs. random (label). CNN attains ≈ 99.8-99.9% accuracy on unprotected SW/HW, enabling a strong plaintext-checking oracle and full key recovery within $\leq 60k$ traces. Under TI-masked HW, accuracy collapses to $\approx 51\%$, rendering the oracle ineffective [38].</p>
<p>Kyber (SW): Decapsulation; labels = secret-key coefficient s_0 (0-3328). CNN with ciphertext-knowledge (5 Conv layers + Dense fusion + 5-layer classifier; RMSprop, lr 10^{-6}) trained on 200k-500k traces (600 samples/trace). Attack phase requires ≤ 50 traces (500k profiling) to reach mean-rank 0 and recover targeted 12-bit key coefficients. Ciphertext knowledge (2 or 4 coeffs) reduces profiling/attack traces needed. No masking/shuffling; full key recovery achieved by iterating per-coefficient attack. [14]</p>
<p>Kyber (SW): Decapsulation; FO re-encryption leakage from PRF/RO execution (software, power/EM). Multi-valued PC oracle via deep NN (6 Conv layers + BN/AvgPool + FC1-FC3 with SELU/Softmax). Training uses μ-class labels from valid ciphertexts. Achieves full key recovery with 576 traces (vs. 3,072 baseline), an 81% reduction at 99.9999% success probability. [36]</p>
<p>Kyber (A, SW): Decapsulation; Adaptive Slimmed Pyramid Network (ASPN) distinguisher. Binary classification/labeling of m_0/m_1 from re-encryption EM traces; 100k-sample traces; 800 train / 200 test per class; accuracies 0.99 (18 mm) to 0.893 (24 mm with clone); full key recovery with 5818.5 traces; ASPN3 optimal; train 39.41 s / test 0.49 s; T-test reduces model size by 94% while reaching 0.973 accuracy [6].</p>
<p>Dilithium-2 (SW): Targets Montgomery-reduction leakage to recover cs_1 (labeled). Architecture: 3 Conv layers (filters 12/24/48; kernels 64/128/256; strides 1/6/1), BN + avg-pool after each, followed by one Dense-Softmax layer (Adam, lr = 4×10^{-4}, 150 epochs, batch=1600). Trained on 200k segments; single-trace cs_1 recovery SR=70.5-74.3%. When fused with LR-based y recovery and COBRA/ILP equation solving, the attack achieves full s_1 key recovery in 1-3 signatures [28].</p>
<p>Dilithium-2/3/5 (SW): Signing; leakage during INTT and Montgomery reduction. Labels = ct_0 coefficients (sign and value). CNN distinguisher: (i) 1-layer CNN for sign; (ii) $2 \times$ Conv (32,64, 3×3) + BN + MaxPool + FC(128,64,ReLU) for value (Adam, CrossEntropyLoss). Trained on 40k ct_0 traces; tested on 10k cs_1/cs_2 samples. Success rates (range [-31,31]): $cs_1/cs_2 = 26.7/36.2\%$ (Dilithium2), 20.5/28.8% (Dilithium3), 22.4/31.5% (Dilithium5). Full s_1, s_2 recovery in 10/27/18 traces using residual-analysis solver [29].</p>

(SW)Firmware, (HW)FPGA, (M)Masked, (A)Anti-Tampering Cover

Table 6: Summary of othes AI-based Techniques SCAs

RF (Random Forest)
<p>Kyber (SW): Decapsulation; labels = HW(m), HW(y) from basemul/fqmul in pointwise multiplication. Random Forest HW classifier trained on clone-device PoIs (CPA-selected); O0 HW accuracy 69–80% (input), 81–85% (output); O3 accuracy \approx70–72%. Simulated attack achieves coefficient GE=0 in \approx671 traces (perfect HW) or \approx8524 traces (95% HW). Practical evaluation recovers 20 secret coefficients with 35–5000 traces. Full-key recovery feasible under blind setting. [30]</p> <p>Kyber512/768/1024 (O): Decapsulation; decryption-failure oracle exploited to build bilateral linear inequalities on secret key coefficients. Oracle remains extractable even with masked/constant-time ciphertext-comparison and sanity-check countermeasures. ML-based contraction uses a Random Forest (300 trees, depth 30) trained on JSD sequences over BP iterations. Filtered/unfiltered cases need 5.2k/8k inequalities. Full key recovery with \approx5.5k (512), 7k (768), 6.75k (1024) inequalities; query factor \approx2.5-2.6 and \approx40-48% query-complexity reduction [27].</p>
LLM (Large Language Model)
<p>Kyber-256 (SW): Decapsulation; <i>operation-type</i> labeling for SPA (256 ops). ChatGPT used as zero-shot classifier (no NN training); segmented traces (max 36 ops/query). 0-shot/general prompts give OPSR=0, but expert prompting (strategies 1&2) enables full private-key recovery, with OPSR\approx0.5 over 10 runs [45].</p> <p>Kyber (R): Post-analysis fortification; SCAR employs an LLM (Falcon-7B) to automatically generate leakage-mitigated RTL by inserting Boolean masking into vulnerable lines flagged by the GNN. The LLM rewrites RTL modules (e.g., <code>intmul</code>) into masked variants; validation via post-synthesis dynamic-power analysis confirms reduced leakage at the modified sites. No AI-based attack performed; LLM used solely for countermeasure synthesis. [35]</p>
GNN (Graph Neural Network)
<p>Kyber (R): Leakage assessment (not attacking); SCAR analyzes Kyber’s RTL CDFG using a GNN (GCN1-GCN2 + FC + sigmoid), trained on AES-Comp (lr=0.01, batch=20, dropout=0.3, 32 epochs). Node-features: vulnerable-path count, degree, Hamming-distance, AND/OR/XOR/MUX ops. Achieves 88.89% accuracy, 95.38% precision, 91.20% recall for Kyber; identifies the <code>intmul</code> module as leakage-prone. [35]</p>
DQN
<p>Kyber (SW,HW): Decapsulation; <i>no leakage labeling</i> (RL is label-free). SPA-GPT uses Deep Q-Network (DQN) with a 4-layer MLP (BN + Dense(40)\times3) to automatically segment a <i>single</i> power trace, since MLP-based Q-networks approximate the Q-table efficiently for large action spaces. Reward = negative mean Euclidean distance between segments. Achieves 100% segmentation accuracy on Kyber traces and recovers the <i>intermediate value crucial for deriving the secret key</i>; no masking defeated, no full-key recovery demonstrated. [43]</p>
DNN (Deep Neural Network)
<p>Kyber512/768/1024 (M, SW): Decapsulation; ($m \neq m'$) labeling. Neural-network-based multi-valued PC-oracle built from a fully connected feed-forward NN (3 hidden layers, 1024 units each; ReLU; Softmax; Adam, lr=0.001; batch=64; 10 epochs). Input uses $t_1 = 3$ PoIs; each oracle query uses $t_1 t_2 = 9$ traces. NN accuracy \approx 98.97%, rising to \geq 99.96% with majority voting. Full-key recovery requires 432 / 648 / 864 traces for Kyber512/768/1024. [42]</p>
RNN (Recurrent Neural Network)
<p>Kyber-768 (M,SW): Fails to recover key. Decapsulation; polytomsg(m)[i] labeling; first-order masked poly tomsg attacked. 50k traces; bitwise segmentation ($256 \times 3 \times 225$); $<$70% accuracy and fails to converge. Attack requires chosen ciphertexts, preprocessing and ECT-based error correction [12]. See Table 4 for successfully MLP attack of this paper.</p>
(SW) Firmware, (HW) FPGA, (R) RTL, (M) Masked, O(Oracle Based)
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="width: 15px; height: 15px; background-color: #f4a460; margin-right: 5px;"></div> Neural / Deep </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="width: 15px; height: 15px; background-color: #a4c6f4; margin-right: 5px;"></div> Classical </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="width: 15px; height: 15px; background-color: #a4f4a4; margin-right: 5px;"></div> Reinforcement / Decision </div> </div>

Additional Tables

Table 7: NIST Standardized and Forthcoming PQC Algorithms

Standard Name	FIPS Standard	FIPS Date / Status	NIST IR	NIST IR Date	Underlying Algorithm	Cryptographic Family	Primary Function
ML-KEM	FIPS 203	2024-08-13 [23]	8413	2022-07-05 [1]	CRYSTALS-Kyber	Lattice-Based (MLWE)	Key Encapsulation (Primary)
ML-DSA	FIPS 204	2024-08-13 [23]	8413	2022-07-05 [1]	CRYSTALS-Dilithium	Lattice-Based (MLWE)	Digital Signature (Primary)
SLH-DSA	FIPS 205	2024-08-13 [23]	8413	2022-07-05 [1]	SPHINCS+	Hash-Based	Digital Signature (Backup)
HQC	Pending	Expected 2027 [24]	8545	2025-03-11 [2]	Hamming-Quasi-Cyclic	Code-Based	Key Encapsulation (Backup)
FN-DSA	FIPS 206 (Draft)	Expected 2025 [25]	8413	2022-07-05 [1]	FALCON	Lattice-Based (NTRU)	Digital Signature (Additional)

Table 8: Notable PQC Candidates Not Selected for Standardization

Algorithm	Family	NIST IR	NIST IR Date	Reason for Not Being Standardized / Dropped
SIKE	Isogeny-Based	8545	March 11, 2025 [2]	A practical key recovery attack was demonstrated using a classical computer, rendering the scheme insecure and leading to its withdrawal from the standardization process [5,32,33].
Classic McEliece	Code-Based	8545	March 11, 2025 [2]	Not selected for standardization due to concerns about very large public key sizes, skepticism about widespread adoption, and a desire to avoid creating standards incompatible with an ongoing ISO effort [2].
BIKE	Code-Based	8545	March 11, 2025 [2]	A Round 4 finalist, but not selected in favor of HQC, which had a more mature and stable security analysis [2,26].
Rainbow	Multivariate	8413	July 5, 2022 [1]	A practical attack in early 2022 broke the scheme, undermining confidence in multivariate signatures and leading to its withdrawal [4,37].

Table 9: Distribution of Quality Assessment Scores

Quality Score	Number of Papers
7.0	1
6.5	2
6.0	2
5.5	9
5.0	8
< 5.0	5
Total	27

References

1. Alagic, G., Apon, D., Cooper, D., Dang, Q., Dang, T., Kelsey, J., Lichtinger, J., Liu, Y.K., Miller, C., Moody, D., Peralta, R., Perlner, R., Robinson, A., Smith-Tone, D.: Status report on the third round of the nist post-quantum cryptography standardization process. Tech. Rep. NIST IR 8413, National Institute of Standards and Technology (9 2022). <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.IR.8413-upd1>
2. Alagic, G., Bros, M., Ciadoux, P., Cooper, D., Dang, Q., Dang, T., Kelsey, J., Lichtinger, J., Liu, Y.K., Miller, C., Moody, D., Peralta, R., Perlner, R., Robinson, A., Silberg, H.: Status report on the fourth round of the nist post-quantum cryptography standardization process. Tech. Rep. NIST IR 8545, National Institute of Standards and Technology (3 2025). <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.IR.8545>
3. Association for Computing Machinery: Acm digital library. Online Database (2025), <https://dl.acm.org/>, comprehensive database for publications from the ACM and affiliated organizations
4. Beullens, W.: Breaking rainbow takes a weekend on a laptop. Cryptology ePrint Archive, Paper 2022/214 (2022), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2022/214>
5. Castryck, W., Decru, T.: An efficient key recovery attack on sidh. Cryptology ePrint Archive, Paper 2022/975 (2022), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2022/975>
6. Chen, P., Li, J., Cheng, W., Cheng, C.: Uncover secrets through the cover: A deep learning-based side-channel attack against kyber implementations with anti-tampering covers. IEEE Transactions on Computers **74**(6), 2159–2167 (06 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TC.2025.3547610>
7. Choi, K.h., Han, J., Han, D.: Single trace analysis of visible vs. invisible leakage for comparison-operation-based CDT sampling. Electronics (Switzerland) **13**(23) (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13234681>
8. Dubrova, E., Ngo, K., Gärtner, J., Wang, R.: Breaking a fifth-order masked implementation of CRYSTALS-kyber by copy-paste. In: Proceedings of the 10th ACM Asia Public-Key Cryptography Workshop. pp. 10–20. APKC '23 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3591866.3593072>
9. Elsevier: Engineering village. Online Database (2025), <https://www.engineeringvillage.com/>, comprehensive database for engineering and applied science literature
10. Elsevier: Scencedirect. Online Database (2025), <https://www.sciencedirect.com/>, database of scientific, technical, and medical research
11. Elsevier: Scopus. Online Database (2025), <https://www.scopus.com/>, large abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature
12. Ganesh, B.S., Ahmed, M.M., Mady, A.: Higher order leakage assessment and neural network-based attack on CRYSTALS-kyber. In: Proceedings of the International Conference on Security and Cryptography. pp. 373 – 380 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5220/0012715700003767>
13. Han, J., Lee, T., Kwon, J., Lee, J., Kim, I.J., Cho, J., Han, D.G., Sim, B.Y.: Single-trace attack on NIST round 3 candidate dilithium using machine learning-based profiling. IEEE Access **9**, 166283–166292 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3135600>
14. Hoang, A.T., Kennaway, M., Pham, D.T., Mai, T.S., Khalid, A., Rafferty, C., O’Neill, M.: Deep learning enhanced side channel analysis on CRYSTALS-kyber. In: 2024 25th International Symposium on Quality Electronic Design (ISQED). pp. 1–8 (04 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISQED60706.2024.10528674>

15. Huang, Z., Wang, H., Cao, B., He, D., Wang, J.: A comprehensive side-channel leakage assessment of CRYSTALS-kyber in IIoT. *Internet of Things* **27**, 101331 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2024.101331>
16. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers: Ieee xplore digital library. Online Database (2025), <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/>, primary database for publications in electrical engineering and computer science
17. International Association for Cryptologic Research: Cryptology eprint archive (2024), <https://eprint.iacr.org/>
18. Jendral, S., Ngo, K., Wang, R., Dubrova, E.: Breaking SCA-protected CRYSTALS-kyber with a single trace. In: 2024 IEEE International Symposium on Hardware Oriented Security and Trust (HOST). pp. 70–73 (05 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/HOST55342.2024.10545390>
19. Ji, Y., Dubrova, E.: A side-channel attack on a masked hardware implementation of crystals-kyber. *Journal of Cryptographic Engineering* **15**(1), 7 (04 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13389-025-00375-7>
20. Ji, Y., Wang, R., Ngo, K., Dubrova, E., Backlund, L.: A side-channel attack on a hardware implementation of CRYSTALS-kyber. In: 2023 IEEE European Test Symposium (ETS). pp. 1–5 (05 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ETS56758.2023.10174000>
21. Kim, I.J., Lee, T.H., Han, J., Sim, B.Y., Han, D.G.: Novel single-trace ML profiling attacks on NIST 3 round candidate dilithium (2020), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2020/1383>
22. Marzougui, S., Ulitzsch, V., Tibouchi, M., Seifert, J.P.: Profiling side-channel attacks on dilithium: A small bit-fiddling leak breaks it all (2022), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2022/106>
23. National Institute of Standards and Technology: Nist releases first 3 finalized post-quantum encryption standards. NIST News (8 2024), <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2024/08/nist-releases-first-3-finalized-post-quantum-encryption-standards>
24. National Institute of Standards and Technology: Nist pqc standardization process: Hqc announced as a 4th round selection. NIST News (3 2025), <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2025/03/nist-pqc-standardization-process-hqc-announced-4th-round-selection>
25. National Institute of Standards and Technology: Nist selects hqc as fifth algorithm for post-quantum encryption. NIST News (3 2025), <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2025/03/nist-selects-hqc-fifth-algorithm-post-quantum-encryption>
26. PQShield: Nist selects hqc for standardization. PQShield Blog (2025), <https://pqshield.com/nist-selects-hqc-for-standardization/>
27. Qiao, K., Wang, Z., Chang, H., Sun, S., Wu, Z., Cheng, J., Ou, C., Wang, A., Zhu, L.: A closer look at the belief propagation algorithm in side-channel attack on cca-secure pqc kem. *Science China Information Sciences* **67**(11), 212302 (10 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11432-024-4150-3>
28. Qiao, Z., Liu, Y., Zhou, Y., Zhao, Y., Chen, S.: Single trace is all it takes: Efficient side-channel attack on dilithium (2024), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2024/512>
29. Qiao, Z., Liu, Y., Zhou, Y., Zhao, Y., Yuan, H., Du, D.: Efficient CNN-based side-channel attacks on dilithium without device access. In: 2025 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS). pp. 1–5 (05 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCAS56072.2025.11043271>

30. Ravi, P., Jap, D., Bhasin, S., Chattopadhyay, A.: Invited paper: Machine learning based blind side-channel attacks on PQC-based KEMs - a case study of kyber KEM. In: 2023 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Computer Aided Design (ICCAD). pp. 01–07 (10 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCAD57390.2023.10323721>
31. Rezaeezade, A., Yap, T., Jap, D., Bhasin, S., Picek, S.: Breaking the blindfold: deep learning-based blind side-channel analysis (2025)
32. Schneier, B.: Sike broken. Schneier on Security Blog (8 2022), <https://www.schneier.com/blog/archives/2022/08/sike-broken.html>
33. SecurityWeek: Nist post-quantum algorithm finalist cracked using classical pc. SecurityWeek News (2022), <https://www.securityweek.com/nist-post-quantum-algorithm-finalist-cracked-using-classical-pc/>
34. Springer: Springer link. Online Database (2025), <https://link.springer.com/>, database for scientific journals, books, and proceedings
35. Srivastava, A., Das, S., Choudhury, N., Psiakis, R., Silva, P.H., Pal, D., Basu, K.: SCAR: Power side-channel analysis at RTL level. IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems **32**(6), 1110–1123 (06 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVLSI.2024.3390601>
36. Tanaka, Y., Ueno, R., Xagawa, K., Ito, A., Takahashi, J., Homma, N.: Multiple-valued plaintext-checking side-channel attacks on post-quantum KEMs. IACR Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems **2023**(3), 473 – 503 (2023), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2022/940>
37. Teske, E.: Nist pqc finalists update: It’s over for the rainbow. Cryptomathic Blog (3 2022), <https://www.cryptomathic.com/blog/nist-pqc-finalists-update-its-over-for-the-rainbow>
38. Ueno, R., Xagawa, K., Tanaka, Y., Ito, A., Takahashi, J., Homma, N.: Curse of re-encryption: A generic power/EM analysis on post-quantum KEMs. IACR Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems **2022**(1), 296 – 322 (2021), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2021/849>
39. Wang, J., Cao, W., Chen, H., Li, H.: Practical side-channel attack on masked message encoding in latticed-based KEM (2022), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2022/859>
40. Wang, R., Gärtner, J., Dubrova, E.: Decompressing dilithium’s public key with fewer signatures using side channel analysis. In: 2025 IEEE 55th International Symposium on Multiple-Valued Logic (ISMVL). pp. 135–140 (06 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMVL64713.2025.00034>
41. Wang, R., Ngo, K., Gärtner, J., Dubrova, E.: Single-trace side-channel attacks on CRYSTALS-dilithium: Myth or reality? (2023), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2023/1931>
42. Wang, Y., Huang, F., Duan, X., Hu, H.: Second-order side-channel attacks on kyber: Targeting the masked hash function. Journal of Cryptologic Research **11**(6), 1415 – 1436 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.13868/j.cnki.jcr.000745>
43. Wang, Z., Ding, Y., Wang, A., Zhang, Y., Wei, C., Sun, S., Zhu, L.: Spa-gpt: General pulse tailor for simple power analysis based on reinforcement learning. IACR Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems **2024**(4), 40–83 (09 2024). <https://doi.org/10.46586/tches.v2024.i4.40-83>
44. Yang, Y., Huang, J., Wang, Z., Ye, J., Sun, Z., Fan, J., Chen, S., Li, H., Li, X., Cao, Y.: A template attack on reduction without reference device on kyber. In: 2023 IEEE 32nd Asian Test Symposium (ATS). pp. 1–6 (10 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ATS59501.2023.10318019>

45. Zhou, W., Wang, A., Ding, Y., Wei, C., Zhang, J., Zhu, L.: One solves all: Exploring ChatGPT's capabilities for fully automated simple power analysis on cryptosystems (2024), <https://eprint.iacr.org/2024/2069>